

Summary Report of the Achievements of K-HEALTHinAIR in Barcelona (Pilot 1) at M36/M48 & Plans until the end of the project lifetime

Academic background and unsolved issues

Exposure to air pollution is considered the most important environmental health risk factor with significant deleterious impacts on physiological developments during early life and accelerated functional decline in the elderly¹. There is also robust evidence of both acute and sustained adverse effects of air pollution on several organs and systems, with respiratory disorders being one of the primary concerns^{2,3,4}.

The harmful effects of indoor air quality (IAQ) on respiratory health have been consistently proven in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma^{5,6,7} showing significant associations between indoor pollutants and symptoms, functional capacity, risk of exacerbations and cardiovascular dysfunction. Recent reports highlighted that the harmful effects of PM pollution on cardiovascular health in patients with COPD can be mitigated by reducing exposure^{4,6} suggesting a potential role for household IAQ monitoring in high-risk patients using low-cost sensors (LCS).

However, there are uncertainties regarding the quality of LCS measurements, and their potential for applicability in healthcare, but also to refine public health policies regarding IAQ. Moreover, there is increasing concern on potential harmful effects of concentrations of indoor pollutants below internationally accepted thresholds.

Core objectives of the Barcelona pilot:

1. Household IAQ monitoring using LCS in a cohort of chronic respiratory patients with obstructive disorders and analysis of the relationships with health status.
2. Analysis of the clinical applicability of LCS.
3. IAQ monitoring using LCS in three additional scenarios: (1) Hospital Clinic of Barcelona (HCB), (2) one metro station of the city, and (3) one city market.
4. Contributions to in vitro/in vivo studies on mechanisms of harmful effects on indoor pollutants on health.

¹ FULLER G ET AL. *Impacts of Air Pollution across the Life Course – Evidence Highlight Note.*; 2023. Accessed February 12, 2025. [https://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2023-04/Imperial College London Projects - impacts of air pollution across the life course – evidence highlight note.pdf](https://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2023-04/Imperial%20College%20London%20Projects%20-%20impacts%20of%20air%20pollution%20across%20the%20life%20course%20-%20evidence%20highlight%20note.pdf)

² CHEN J ET AL. LONG-TERM EXPOSURE TO FINE PARTICLE ELEMENTAL COMPONENTS AND NATURAL AND CAUSE-SPECIFIC MORTALITY-A POOLED ANALYSIS OF EIGHT EUROPEAN COHORTS WITHIN THE ELAPSE PROJECT. *ENVIRON HEALTH PERSPECT.* 2021;129(4):47009. doi:10.1289/EHP8368

³ Turner MC et al. *Clean air in Europe for all! Taking stock of the proposed revision to the ambient air quality directives: a joint ERS, HEI and ISEE workshop report.* *Eur Respir J.* 2023;62(4). doi:10.1183/13993003.01380-2023

⁴ RAJU S ET AL. INDOOR AIR POLLUTION AND IMPAIRED CARDIAC AUTONOMIC FUNCTION IN CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE. *AM J RESPIR CRIT CARE MED.* 2023;207(6):721-730. doi:10.1164/RCCM.202203-0523OC

⁵ HANSEL NN ET AL. IN-HOME AIR POLLUTION IS LINKED TO RESPIRATORY MORBIDITY IN FORMER SMOKERS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE. *AM J RESPIR CRIT CARE MED.* 2013;187(10):1085-1090. doi:10.1164/RCCM.201211-1987OC.

⁶ HANSEL NN ET AL. Randomized Clinical Trial of Air Cleaners to Improve Indoor Air Quality and Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Health Results of the CLEAN AIR Study. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 2022;205(4):421-430. doi:10.1164/RCCM.202103-0604OC/SUPPL_FILE/DISCLOSURES.PDF

⁷ Balmes JR et al. *Tiny Particles, Big Health Impacts (editorial).* *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 2024;210(11):1291-1292. doi:10.1164/rccm.202407-1476ED

Achievements of the Barcelona pilot at M36

Objective 1 - Household IAQ monitoring and relationships with health status

The details of the protocol for the two-year follow-up of a cohort of 205 patients with COPD and co-morbidities, bronchiectasis, or asthma were reported in⁸. Preliminary results of household IAQ monitoring are described in⁹. Moreover, the evolution of the hybrid care intervention carried out in the cohort during the first eighteen-month period of the follow-up, as well as the co-design process done to refine the intervention, are reported in¹⁰.

Briefly, in the early study⁹ on household IAQ was profiled prospectively over two months using LCS that logged CO₂, PM_{2.5} and formaldehyde every 10 minutes. For each pollutant, dwellings were classified as Good, Moderate or Unhealthy according to the Global Open Air Quality Standards thresholds. Clinical surveillance was conducted over the preceding 12 months, with pulmonary exacerbations requiring hospitalization as the primary endpoint and all-cause emergency department visits as an exploratory endpoint.

The reported results indicate that half of homes (92; 51.7%) had at least one pollutant in an at-risk category. The burden was driven by PM_{2.5}: 40.1% of dwellings were classified as at risk (32.8% Moderate; 7.3% Unhealthy). Formaldehyde exceeded the low-risk threshold in 22 homes (12.4%). The prevalence of smokers rose steeply across PM_{2.5} categories ($p < 0.001$). Despite this high prevalence of at-risk IAQ, the distribution of IAQ categories was comparable between patients with and without hospitalised exacerbations; a similar pattern was observed for all-cause emergency department visits.

From this study⁹, it was concluded that Impaired IAQ is a prevalent phenomenon, PM_{2.5} driven and strongly linked to indoor smoking. IAQ risk categories did not associate directly with unplanned hospitalisations, instead, risk was driven by multimorbidity burden, pulmonary disease severity, and history of previous events. However, the retrospective, registry-based, clinical analysis using unplanned hospitalizations as outcome variable was judged as suboptimal, confirming the need the approach reported in¹⁰, wherein early characterization and enhanced management of community-based exacerbations in the patients of the cohort administering a hybrid care intervention constitutes the core objective.

The rationale behind the intervention reported in¹⁰ is that the efficient management of community-based management of exacerbations in chronic respiratory patients is an unmet need mainly due to the symptoms-based definition of exacerbation, but also partly explained by the heterogeneities seen in chronic obstructive respiratory patients. However, it has been proved that a patient-centred hybrid care intervention combining: (1) health risk assessment (HRA) aiming at personalizing the intervention, (2) digitally enabled adaptive case management (ACM), and (3) nurse-led coordination to deliver personalized care for high-risk patients allows objective characterization of community-based exacerbations overcoming current limitations in the management of these patients. The study protocol reported in^{8,10} has the following twofold aim within the project K-HEALTHinAIR. Firstly, improve the prospective analysis of the relationships between household IAQ and health status targeting a core outcome variable the management of community-based exacerbations. Secondly, assess healthcare value generation

⁸ GÓMEZ-LÓPEZ A ET AL. Protocol for the enhanced management of multimorbid patients with COPD and severe asthma: role of indoor air quality. *BMJ Open Respir Res.* 2025;12(1). doi:10.1136/bmjresp-2024-002589.

⁹ Ruben Gonzalez-Colom, et al. Should Household Air Quality Monitoring Be Considered in Selected Asthma & COPD Patients? medRxiv 2025.09.11.25335550; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.09.11.25335550>

¹⁰ GÓMEZ-LÓPEZ A ET AL. BRIDGING THE GAP BETWEEN CLINICAL TRIALS AND REAL-WORLD PRACTICE: A HYBRID CARE APPROACH FOR HIGH-RISK CHRONIC RESPIRATORY PATIENTS. MEDRXIV 2025.09.11.25335555; doi: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.1101/2025.09.11.25335555](https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.09.11.25335555)

of the hybrid care intervention and evaluate its applicability in routine clinical care for enhanced management of chronic patients showing high-risk of exacerbations leading to unplanned hospitalizations, beyond the current EU project. As reported, the study protocol includes two parallel activities: (1) Prospective follow-up of the cohort, and (2) Co-design of the components of the hybrid care intervention using Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) approach with four cycles of six-month duration each. Achievements at M36 correspond to the end of the third PDSA cycle (PDSA-3).

The preliminary results seen in¹⁰ after eighteen months of follow-up of the cohort (PDSA-3) indicate two promising disruptive innovations of the refined hybrid care intervention, already achieved at M36: (1) for the first time, provides an objective characterization and management of exacerbations at community level in these patients (currently based only on symptoms), and (2) shows high potential for sustainable scale up, and transferability, of the approach to different profiles of patients with non-communicable diseases.

Objective 2 - Analysis of the clinical applicability of LCS

The outcomes of the study reported in⁹ support the feasibility and potential value of remote IAQ assessment, for PM and formaldehyde, using LCS in respiratory medicine. While not a substitute for high-precision equipment, LCS offers a scalable, affordable, and patient-friendly solution for environmental assessment. Further work is needed regarding: (1) quality of assessment of VOC, (2) evolution of portable sensors, as well as (3) enrichment with additional sensors (oxidants, etc...).

The ongoing follow-up will provide critical evidence to inform future recommendations and define the clinical utility of IAQ assessment as part of holistic value-based care strategies for chronic respiratory diseases. Such approaches could represent an important step toward addressing the environmental determinants of respiratory health, contributing to the management of community-based exacerbations, and reducing the substantial burden of preventable hospitalizations.

Objective 3 - IAQ monitoring using LCS in three additional scenarios

Hospital Clinic of Barcelona (HCB): A hospital-wide indoor air quality (IAQ) assessment, since June 2023, was conducted at HCB to characterise conditions in representative spaces and to derive operational recommendations. The information sources comprised a network of calibrated, low-cost sensors (LCS) installed in main entrance and waiting areas, inpatient wards, intensive care units (ICUs), consultation rooms and technical laboratories. Continuous measurements included CO₂, PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀, total volatile organic compounds (tVOC), formaldehyde, temperature and relative humidity. Time series were processed into GO-AQS summary indicators to harmonise interpretation across areas and pollutants.

Data integration followed a two-step process. First, each zone's time series were aggregated into the share of time spent in performance categories (good, moderate concern, needs intervention), yielding a comparable view of ventilation effectiveness, particulate events and chemical loads. Second, area-level dashboards were used to contrast spatial patterns and to identify short-lived events against background conditions. This framework enabled concise, actionable messages for facility management without resorting to complex statistics.

Results showed marked heterogeneity across the hospital. ICUs maintained consistently excellent IAQ under regulated mechanical ventilation, with stable CO₂ and very low particulate levels and only minimal VOC and trace formaldehyde. In contrast, consultation rooms and waiting areas exhibited the most frequent CO₂ elevations, indicating a mismatch between real-world occupancy and air renewal during busy periods. Inpatient wards generally presented

low-to-moderate PM with occasional bursts linked to cleaning or movement, whereas laboratories displayed higher and more variable VOC burdens, sometimes accompanied by localised formaldehyde peaks. Overall, indoor–outdoor coupling appeared limited, supporting the interpretation that most observed peaks were locally generated.

The combined evidence supports targeted improvements. Ventilation control should be aligned with actual occupancy in consultation and waiting areas, using CO₂-guided or occupancy-based strategies. Selection and timing of cleaning and disinfection products should be optimised to reduce VOC spikes and to avoid unnecessary exposure. Finally, continuous IAQ tracking should be maintained in strategic spaces for early detection and response, with ICU good practices replicated where feasible. The GO-AQS approach proved effective to separate background from events, highlight zone-specific risks and prioritise practical interventions to protect patients and staff in complex hospital settings. It is of note that microbiome samplings are still under analysis.

Area	CO ₂	PM _{2.5}	VOCs	Formaldehyde
Main Entrance / Waiting	● High Peaks	● Occasional	● Moderate	● Low
Inpatient Wards	● Variable	● Occasional	● Moderate	● Low
ICU	● Stable	● Very Low	● Minimal	● Trace only
Consultation Rooms	● Frequent	● Moderate	● Accumulated	● Low Peaks
Laboratories / Technical	● Acceptable	● Variable	● High	● Local Peaks

● = Good | ● = Moderate concern | ● = Needs intervention

Table 1. GO-AQS matrix summarising IAQ by hospital area (CO₂, PM_{2.5}, VOCs, formaldehyde). Green = good; yellow = moderate concern; red = needs intervention.

Metro station: Since October 2024, assessment of IAQ during one-year is ongoing in one of the Metro stations of the city (Barcelona). Continuous measurements include CO₂, PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀, total volatile organic compounds (VOC), formaldehyde, temperature and relative humidity. The study protocol shows close similarities to one described for the HCB. Time series will be processed into GO-AQS summary indicators to harmonise interpretation across areas and pollutants. The results will be compared with historical measurements done in the same metro station and the study outcomes are expected to feed future strategies to enhance IAQ at city level.

City Market: Since August 2024, assessment of IAQ during one-year was done in one of the city markets (Mercat de la Concepció) which was selected because no other activities, like restaurants, were done in the setting. The study protocol showed close similarities to the one described for the HCB and the metro station. The results are currently being processed.

Objective 4 - Contributions to in vitro/in vivo studies: At consortium level, a decision was taken (2024, Q3) to focus on the study of the harmful effects, as well as their mechanisms, of formaldehyde in epithelial cells from lung and skin using in vitro models elaborated within the project in collaboration with other partners of the IDEAL cluster. There is a plan to further explore high VOC levels (formaldehyde) observed in some outpatients' homes one of the HCB laboratories (see **Table 1**), perform a preventive intervention cleaning the ambient and explore the relationships of the results with the outcomes of the in vitro models.

Last year (M36-M48) project challenges in Barcelona

Objective 1 – Ongoing household IAQ monitoring and relationships with health status

Completion of the prospective analysis of the relationships between household IAQ monitoring and community-based exacerbations constitutes a central aspect of the project to be achieved during the last semester of the follow-up of the cohort which corresponds to the fourth PDSA cycle (1st September 2025 – 1st March 2026) in the co-design process.

As described in detail in ¹⁰ (**Table 4**), the activities during the period will be oriented toward facing the following four challenges: (1) Identification of target candidates for a personalized hybrid care intervention, (2) Refinement of the objective characterization of acute episodes, (3) Optimization of the administration of the hybrid care intervention in a real world scenario, (4) Identification of actionable factors for improving household IAQ. While the later will be described under Objective 2, the activities to face the first three challenges are summarized below:

Challenge 1 - Identification of the target candidates and personalization of the hybrid care intervention: The baseline holistic assessment of the cohort reported in¹⁰, as well as the longitudinal contacts between the nurse case manager and participants over the first 18 months of the follow-up (PDSA-3), enabled the identification of six clinical groups: two within HCB's Severe Asthma program (A1–A2) and four within the community-based AISBE program (C1–C4), showing different requirements regarding the hybrid care intervention, as detailed in **Table 2**.

TABLE 2 – The six clinical groups defined in the study cohort

Grup	Main features	Hybrid Care implications
Severe Asthma Program at HCB (n=48)		
A1 n=23 (47.92%)	Severe asthma, stages 5 and 6, clinically stable without requiring interactions with the nurse	Only requiring an active communication channel with the nurse without scheduled actions.
A2 n=25 (52.08%)	Exacerbations and/or other problems (mental disorders: mostly anxiety/depression, social frailty, ...) trigger frequent interactions with the nurse	Target candidates for a hybrid care intervention. Specific needs identified for clinically unstable patients with severe asthma and obesity.
Community-based AISBE Program (n=135)		
C1 n=50 (37.04%)	Mild-moderate lung disease (i.e. COPD, GOLD I or II) with few symptoms and unproblematic co-morbidities.	Not candidates for the intervention. Potential inclusion of specific patients to be assessed individually.
C2 n=18 (13.33%)	Moderate-severe lung disease, and/or rapid disease progress and/or history of severe exacerbations	Target candidates for the hybrid care intervention with shared care agreements with specialized care
C3 n=33 (24.44%)	Moderate-severe lung disease with problematic co-morbidities and/or social frailty.	Target candidates requiring a personalized intervention.
C4 n=34 (25.19%)	Very severe lung disease (i.e. COPD, GOLD IV) often under home respiratory therapies.	Target candidate interacting closely with an advanced respiratory nurse.

One of the key goals of the period will be refining already existing health risk predictive modelling^{11,12} for patients' stratification and personalization of the hybrid care intervention. The co-design process identified three target clinical program modalities for the hybrid care intervention, beyond K-HEALTHinAIR, namely: (1) high-risk cases identified in the community, (2) vulnerable patients at discharge from hospital, as part of post-discharge care programs, and (3) selected patients managed in specialized outpatient clinics

Challenge 2 - Objective characterization of community-based exacerbations: The objective characterization of the community-based exacerbations will be a key step forward in respiratory medicine for enhanced management of community-based acute episodes, but also to better understand, and modulate, the prognosis of these patients. The results already obtained in K-HEALTHinAIR indicate that the evolution of three key covariates from baseline to the acute episode and during recovery will facilitate the objective characterization of the acute events and assist clinical decision making in these patients.

Patients' data capture and processing for two of these covariates: lung function and symptoms, has been fully solved during the co-design process, well before the end of PDSA-3. That is, home-based patients self-administered Oscillometry on daily basis has shown to provide remote essential information on lung function to the nurse case manager. Likewise, daily patients self-administered short questionnaires on symptoms (visual-analogue scale), using the App, are remotely collected by the nurse.

However, further studies are planned during PDSA-4 for better capturing, and processing, data on heart rate variability (HRV) which is the third pillar for characterization of the exacerbations. It is well-known that HRV reflects the balance between vagal and sympathetic tones of the autonomic regulatory system, providing information on cardiovascular function but also on the impact of the acute episode at body system level.

Challenge 3 - Optimization of the administration of the hybrid care intervention: The basic characteristics of the hybrid care intervention, as defined at the end of the PDSA-3, are summarized in **Table 3**. The digital support to the hybrid care intervention currently provided by the Health Circuit platform was reported in¹³.

Briefly, the key features are: i) Multichannel communication between key professionals and patient ii) Shared care plans across healthcare tiers with an Adaptive Case Management (ACM) approach allowing flexibility in front of unexpected events and to specificities of different service providers, iii) Patients' data capture (short questionnaires, testing and monitoring physiological data), iv) Cloud-based architecture to enable scalability and i) Standard-based interoperability with existing corporate-specific health information systems.

Household IAQ assessment with the current LCS showed usefulness in patients presenting refractoriness to standard therapies. Accordingly, they should be considered as one component of the intervention in selected individuals in whom poor IAQ is an actionable factor. Further developments may likely open novel perspectives for the use of LCS in clinical care.

¹¹ González-Colom R et al. Computational modelling for prevention of unplanned hospital admissions in multimorbid patients. *J Med Internet Res*. Published online 2023. doi:10.2196/40846

¹² González-Colom R et al. PhD Thesis. Predictive Modelling for Personalized Multimorbidity Management. University of Barcelona, 29th January 2024. (<http://hdl.handle.net/10803/691632>)

¹³ HERRANZ C ET AL. A Practice-Proven Adaptive Case Management Approach for Innovative Health Care Services (Health Circuit): Cluster Randomized Clinical Pilot and Descriptive Observational Study. *J Med Internet Res*. 2023;25:e47672. doi:10.2196/47672

Table 3 – Main characteristics of the hybrid care intervention²²

Elements in a Digitally Enabled Care Continuum Setting	Clinical programs
<p>Pro-active patient: fulfilling inclusion criteria for the program and empowering self-management. Accessibility to the nurse through a multimedia communication channel (<i>App</i>) and digitally enabled with the patient’s self-capture data system which includes structured and non-structured data, through self-administered short questionnaires, and real-time monitoring of physiological variables, such as HR, HRV, activity levels, pulse oximetry, etc... (<i>wrist sensor</i>)</p>	<p>Community-based AISBE program: included co-morbid patients with chronic obstructive disorders and an AMG^{26,27,32} scoring above percentile eighty in the health risk regional population pyramid. The patients have as a reference physician the general practitioner. The interactions with other service modalities are fully aligned with the pre-existing shared care agreements at health district level (520 k citizens).</p> <p>Severe Asthma Clinic program: included asthma patients, stages 5 and 6, controlled by one pneumologist from the tertiary hospital (HCB). One nurse case manager ascribed to the study conducted the hybrid care intervention.</p>
<p>Nurse case manager: based in the community or at specialized clinics, depending upon the clinical program. Accessibility to the patient and to the reference physician (and other healthcare professionals) through a multimedia communication channel. Digitally enabled with the professional’s dashboard</p>	
<p>Reference physician: primary care physician or specialist depending upon the clinical program. Accessibility to the nurse case manager (to other healthcare professionals and to the patient) through a multimedia communication channel.</p>	
Management of clinically stable patients	
<p>-The first step is the patient’s motivational interview conducted by the nurse aimed at: (1) To empower the patient for self-management of their condition, and (2) To facilitate the collaborative development of a patient’s tailored care plan, with a holistic approach, agreed upon by the patient, the nurse, and the reference physician.</p> <p>-The care plan forms the basis for the patient’s periodic follow-up by the nurse case manager, with most interactions taking place through the established communication channel. In all cases, the management plan takes into consideration the diversity of patients’ profiles.</p> <p>-The clinical management plan is fully aligned with the standard care recommended for each respiratory diagnosis: COPD¹, Asthma² and Bronchiectasis³.</p>	
Management of acute episodes	
<p>-In the event of a worsening of clinical conditions, the patient can contact the nurse case manager through the communication channel. The contact triggers the process of identifying a potential exacerbation, based on the patient’s reported symptoms, and the clinical judgement of the nurse who will be able to interact with the reference physician to decide on further steps needed for the diagnosis and management of the acute episode whatever are its characteristics: i) lung-related events: exacerbation or complication such as pneumonia or thromboembolism, etc..., ii) non-pulmonary dyspnoea, or iii) dyspnoea of mixed origin.</p> <p>- Home-based management of the acute episode activates: i) close follow-up of the patient, remote or face-to-face, by the nurse case manager, ii) daily patient’s self-administration of short questionnaires for symptoms assessment, as well as measurements of Oscillometry and monitoring of physiological variables (HRV) with a wrist device, and iii) adjustment of the therapeutic plan in agreement with the reference physician. This action plan will be maintained for one or two weeks depending upon the patient’s progress.</p>	

HR: Heart Rate; HRV: Heart Rate Variability; AISBE: Integrated Social and Health Care Based on Evidence; AMG: Adjusted Morbidity Groups; HCB: Hospital Clínic de Barcelona; HRV: Heart Rate Variability; mMRC: Modified Medical Research Council Dyspnoea Scale; CAT: COPD Assessment Test; COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease.

Two well-defined objectives aiming at optimization of the digital support to the hybrid care intervention will be further addressed (PDSA-4) to be achieved beyond the project lifetime, are:

1. Identification of customized modules of digital support, including clinical decision support tools, useful to match intensity and temporality of the support with patients' needs in a cost-effective manner.
2. Explore the development of a novel voice-optimized interface, based on conversational agents powered by Large Language Models (GenAI), for patients with low digital literacy and/or those requiring transient continuous home-based monitoring.

Objective 2 - Analysis of the clinical applicability of LCS

Completion of the analysis of the follow-up of the cohort, as well as the results of the recently implemented protocols aiming at testing the use of filters for cleaning indoor air in selected patients' homes, will provide a robust basis for generating specific recommendations for use of LCS in the assessment, and preventive management, of these patients.

Moreover, the analysis of the performance of LCS in different scenarios will facilitate the assessment of future perspectives of LCS in terms of portability, VOCs measurements, as well as future incorporations of additional sensors (i.e. oxidants, allergens, microbiome, etc...) potentially useful in clinical care.

Objective 3 – Consolidate outcomes of IAQ monitoring with LCS in three scenarios

Hospital Clinic of Barcelona (HCB): During 2025 (Q4), further elaboration of already collected data on VOCs, and microbiome, at HCB will facilitate an integrated analysis of factors modulating IAQ in the Hospital. Such analysis will foster the development of synergies between inhouse strategies for clean indoor air and outcomes generated during K-Health in Air lifetime regarding innovations in the applicability of LCS. Two types of actions are scheduled for 2026: (1) The elaboration of a public report integrating the knowledge generated by K-Health in Air and its impact on future IAQ policy at HCB, and (2) Specific study protocols are planned to further analyze VOCs in the In Vitro Fertilization Unit and in the Pathology Lab (**Table 1**).

Metro station (Barceloneta) and City Market (Concepció): The information of the one-year monitoring of the two scenarios will be elaborated during 2025. The outcomes will be shared at consortium level and with the city entities responsible for the two services, metro and market, aiming at enriching their strategies for cleaning indoor air.

Objective 4 - Contributions to in vitro/in vivo studies

The outcomes of in vitro studies will be shared at consortium level aiming at establishing synergies with the planned VOC studies for 2026 at HCB: Pathology Lab and In Vitro Fertilization Unit.

Conclusions

Household IAQ monitoring and health status: Data collection in the study cohort will end in February 2026. Despite interim analyses of specific issues are regularly done, expected preliminary outcomes of the entire program will be achieved in March-April 2026, whereas final conclusions will be released at the end of the project lifetime.

Key expected outcomes are: (1) Definition of the role of LCS in healthcare and recommendations for future developments; (2) Beyond SoA achievements in terms of objective characterization of community-based exacerbations in chronic obstructive respiratory patients with relevant implications in respiratory medicine; and (3) Consolidation of the hybrid care intervention for enhanced management of chronic patients. Last, but not least, K-Health in Air has generated innovative initiatives fostering cost-effective strategies for digital support of chronic patients to be developed beyond the project lifetime.

IAQ characterization of Hospital, Metro and City Marked: The project will contribute to assess the role of LCS for the characterization, and monitoring, IAQ in public settings. The information collected will hopefully generate synergies with the IAQ strategies promoted by the responsible entities.